

IN VITRO REGENERATION OF CALOTROPIS PROCERA (AIT.) R.BR. THROUGH AXILLARY SHOOT BUD

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Abstract

Calotropis procera (Ait.) R.Br., commonly called as “Akra” belongs to the family Asclepiadaceae. It is a common xerophytic plant which is widely distributed in Asia, Africa and Northeast of Brazil. *C. procera* has a long history of usage in traditional medicines due to the presence of wide range of medicinally important chemical compounds which includes cardiac glycosides, flavonoids, phenolic compounds, terpenoids. Back in the history Hindu physicians used secretions and extracts from different parts of *C. procera* (root, root bark, leaves, flowers and latex) as a remedy for different ailments and this account poses an image of *C. procera* as ‘single cure of various sufferings’. In present study the response of axillary bud explants varied in season of collection of explants. The axillary explants collected in the winter season (November to January) showed best response and about 80% explants were achieved surface sterilized on 0.1% HgCl₂ for 6-7 minutes. In present investigation BAP 13.32 μM in MS semisolid medium was found optimum for in vitro regeneration of 6-7 shoots in 96-97 % of aseptically inoculated explants with 7-6 cm length in a period of 3-4 weeks. IBA (4.92 μM) in MS ½ strength medium was found optimum for regeneration of 5-6 fast growing (12.9 cm) roots in 92-93 % micro-shoots in a period of 16-18 days.

Keywords: *Calotropis procera*, axillary bud explants, plant growth regulators, plant regeneration, multiplication.

INTRODUCTION

Calotropis procera (Ait.) R.Br., commonly called as “Akra” belongs to the family Asclepiadaceae. It is a common xerophytic plant which is widely distributed in Asia, Africa and Northeast of Brazil (Ramos et al., 2006). It is one of the most popular ingredients of

ancient medicines due to the presence of wide range of medicinally important chemical compounds which includes cardiac glycosides, flavonoids, phenolic compounds, terpenoids (Mueen Ahmed et al., 2005; Joshi et al., 2009).

This plant is a very promising source of ascaricidal, schizonticidal, anti-bacterial, anthelmintic, insecticidal, anti-inflammatory, anti-diarrhoeal, larvicidal and cytotoxic chemicals. Different compounds like norditerpenic esters, organic carbonates, the cysteine protease procerain, alkaloids, flavonoids, sterols as well as numerous types of cardenolides have provided this plant for centuries with scientist's interest (Juncker et al., 2009).

The natural habitats for medicinal plants are disappearing fast with increasing environmental and geopolitical instabilities and thus it is increasingly difficult to acquire plant derived compounds. This has prompted industries, as well as scientists to consider the possibilities of investigation into cell cultures as an alternative supply for the production of plant pharmaceuticals (Mulabagal and Tsay, 2004). Plants propagated by *in vitro* techniques showed less variation in the content of secondary metabolites than its cultivated/wild counterpart (Yamada et al., 1991).

Reports are available on *in vitro* propagation of several other species of Asclepiadaceae which have been manipulated in culture using nodal segments on MS full-strength medium fortified with various plant growth regulator combination. These included, *Asclepias currassavica* (Pramanik and Datta, 1986), *Tylophora indica* (Chattopadhyay et al., 1992), *Hemidesmus indicus* (Sharma and Yelne, 1995), *Gymnema elegans* (Komalavalli and Rao, 1997), *Holostemma annulare* (Sudha et al., 1998), *Decalepis hamiltonii* (Bais et al., 2000; Anitha and Pullaiah, 2002), *Cynanchum callialatum* (Raghu Ramulu et al., 2002), and *Holostemma adakodien* (Martin, 2002).

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Clonal propagation:

Young (juvenile) and healthy nodal and terminal bud explants of *Calotropis procera* were collected from Government College, Ajmer (Rajasthan) and surrounding areas in winter season for establishment of *in vitro* cultures. The nodal leaves were

removed from the explants and they were cut into small pieces (2-3 cm) to give 1 node per piece. These explants were washed under running tap water then treated with tween-80 solution for about 15 min followed by several washings with tap water and finally rinsed with distilled water. Then these washed explants were treated with different concentrations of various surface sterilizing agents for different duration of treatment viz. mercuric chloride (0.1-0.5 % w/v), sodium hypo-chloride (1-3 % v/v), 90 % ethanol and hydrogen peroxide solution (5-10 % w/v). After the treatment of surface sterilization with suitable agent (0.1 % mercuric chloride) these explants were washed for 4-5 times with autoclaved distilled water for removal of the traces of surface sterilizing agent from the surface of explant. The explants were also treated with some specific fungicides where fungal contaminants were observed in the explants. All the procedures for the development of *in vitro* cultures were carried out inside a laminar air flow cabinet (Yoriko, New Delhi) under aseptic conditions.

Culture media:

The glasswares used for *in vitro* propagation consists of 150 X 25 mm Riviera and Borosil test tubes, Corning and Borosil flasks (100 ml, 250 ml, 500 ml and 1000 ml), pipettes, measuring cylinders (100 ml, 500 ml and 1000 ml) and Borosil petri plates (90 mm). In most of the experiments the jam bottles with polypropylene lids were used for initiation and multiplication of cultures. Glassware were thoroughly brushed with alkaline detergent teepol and then washed in running water. These were then treated with hot Chromic acid (mixture of $K_2Cr_2O_7 + H_2SO_4 + H_2O$) followed by thorough washing with tap water. All the glasswares, cotton plugs, polypropylene lids, forceps, scalpels and distilled water were sterilized in autoclave at $121^\circ C$ with 15 pound per square inch (psi) pressure for 40-45 minutes and then dried in hot air dryer.

Powders of all the chemicals and plant growth regulators which were used throughout the period of study for media preparation are of pure or analytical grade and were procured from British Drug House (BDH), Mumbai, India, Sigma Chemical Co. (St. Louis, USA), HiMedia Laboratories, Mumbai, India, Qualigens Fine Chemical Co., Mumbai, India and Loba chemie, Mumbai, India.

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MS basal medium (Murashige and Skoog, 1962) is composed of inorganic salts, vitamins, amino acids, plant growth regulators, carbohydrates and the gelling agent. Sucrose (30000 mg/l) was used as a source of carbohydrate in all the nutrient media. The pH of medium was adjusted to 5.8 ± 0.2 with 0.5N NaOH and 0.1N HCl solutions and agar-agar (6000-8000 mg/l) was used as solidifying agent in the media. Then 15 to 20 ml and 35 to 40 ml medium was poured into washed and dried test tubes and culture bottles respectively followed by autoclaving of media at 121°C with 15 psi pressure for 15-17 minutes.

Various plant growth regulators like BAP, Kin, IAA and NAA at different concentrations individually or in combination for shoot proliferation. The regenerated microshoots were rooted on $\frac{1}{2}$ strength MS medium supplemented with different concentrations of auxins like IAA, NAA and IBA.

Surface sterilized explants were inoculated into MS medium and after 3-4 weeks of incubation, the initiated cultures (multiple shoots/cluster) were sectioned into one node piece. These nodal segments were transferred into fresh semi-solid media. The shootlets derived from each explant were observed as individual to determine the total number of plants produced from single shoot. These steps were repeated after every 3-4 weeks for the next sub-culturing for the further multiplication of *in vitro* raised cultures by sub-culturing them onto same or modified media. For root formation the *in vitro* developed shoots were transferred into MS medium of $\frac{1}{2}$ strength with various root inducing hormones as a low salt medium is found satisfactory for rooting of shoots in large number of plant species.

The cultures were maintained in the growth room with temperature conditions $25 \pm 2^{\circ}\text{C}$, with a photoperiod of 16 hrs daylight and 8 hrs night break under the cool white fluorescent light of average 2000-2500 lux (cool white fluorescent tube light 40 W GE) and Relative humidity (RH) 60-70 %.

These rooted micro-shoots were transferred to glass bottle $\frac{1}{4}$ filled with soilrite mixture which is composed of vermiculite, peat moss and perlite in equal ratio for *in vitro* hardening for 10-15 days. The soilrite was moistened with Hoagland's liquid medium prior to inoculation of rooted plantlets. These plantlets were then transferred to earthen pots containing soil mixture. The different soil mixtures in various ratios were tried for pot transfer of plantlets. In *Calotropis*

procera the soil of natural habitat, vermiculite and gravels were used in the pots. The plants were transferred in the pots. The pots were put in a hardening unit or in a green house under a gradient of temperature (30-35°C) and relative humidity (70-45 %) from pad to fan section of green house. After keeping micro plants in hardening unit for 30 days they were finally shifted to the shade house and then to the open field conditions. Data were recorded after 3-4 weeks of culture. Each experiment was repeated three times and five replicates were used for shoot regeneration and shoot multiplication; ten replicates were used for root induction and survival rate.

RESULTS

In present study the response of axillary bud explants varied in season of collection of explants. The axillary explants collected in the winter season (November to January) showed best response and about 80 % explants were achieved surface sterilized on 0.1 % HgCl₂ for 6-7 minutes. In present investigation BAP 13.32 µM in MS semisolid medium was found optimum (Table 1) for *in vitro* regeneration of 6-7 shoots in 96-97 % of aseptically inoculated explants with 7-8 cm length in a period of 3-4 weeks (Fig. 1). The maximum M-M (Multiplication to Multiplication) and M-R (Multiplication to Rooting) was observed on MS medium containing 13.32µM BAP (Table 2) which were 7-8 fold and 12-13 fold respectively (Fig. 2).

IBA (4.92 µM) in MS ½ strength medium was found optimum (Table 3) for regeneration of 5-6 fast growing (12.9 cm) roots in 92-93 % micro-shoots in a period of 16-18 days (Fig. 3).

During investigation total 500 shoots rooted on ½ strength MS medium were placed for *in vitro* hardening (Fig. 4) out of which 490 (98 %) platelets were survived and these were transferred to the green house for *ex vitro* hardening (Fig. 5) for 2-3 weeks and out of which 450 plantlets (92 %) were survived from which 405 plantlets were survived under field conditions (Fig. 6). It was observed form the data of results that overall 81 % survival of tissue culture raised plants of *C. procera* was recorded from rooting to field conditions.

Table 1. Shoot regeneration from internode explants of *C. procera* on MS semisolid medium with different concentrations of BAP.

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S.No.	BAP (μ M)	Percentage of explant sprouted (Mean \pm SD)	Number of shoots per explant (Mean \pm SD)	Shoot length (cm) (Mean \pm SD)
1	0.0	50.0 \pm 1.41	1.4 \pm 0.55	2.1 \pm 0.22
2	2.22	59.6 \pm 1.67	2.8 \pm 1.10	2.3 \pm 0.22
3	4.44	65.6 \pm 1.67	3.2 \pm 1.10	3.4 \pm 0.43
4	6.66	72.8 \pm 1.10	4.0 \pm 1.41	3.6 \pm 0.33
5	8.88	82.0 \pm 1.41	4.8 \pm 1.10	4.7 \pm 0.19
6	11.10	83.2 \pm 1.10	5.6 \pm 0.89	5.6 \pm 0.30
7	13.32	96.8 \pm 1.64	6.0 \pm 1.41	7.6 \pm 0.30
8	15.54	90.4 \pm 1.67	5.2 \pm 1.79	6.5 \pm 0.36
9	17.76	82.0 \pm 1.41	4.4 \pm 0.89	5.3 \pm 0.31
10	19.98	76.4 \pm 1.67	3.6 \pm 0.89	5.3 \pm 0.16
11	22.20	73.2 \pm 1.10	3.2 \pm 1.10	4.3 \pm 0.18

$P < 0.05$; Each value represents the Mean \pm Standard Deviation (SD) of 10 replicates in three repeated experiments. **BAP**=Benzyl Amino Purine

Table 2. Shoot multiplication from regenerated internode explants of *C. procera* on MS semisolid medium with different concentrations of BAP.

S.No.	BAP (μ M)	Rate of M-M (Mean \pm SD)	Rate of M-R (Mean \pm SD)
1	0.0	2.4 \pm 0.89	4.4 \pm 0.55
2	2.22	3.6 \pm 0.55	6.2 \pm 0.45
3	4.44	4.4 \pm 0.55	7.6 \pm 0.55
4	6.66	5.2 \pm 0.45	9.2 \pm 0.45
5	8.88	5.6 \pm 0.55	9.6 \pm 0.55
6	11.10	6.8 \pm 0.45	10.2 \pm 0.84
7	13.32	7.8 \pm 0.84	12.4 \pm 0.55
8	15.54	7.2 \pm 0.45	11.4 \pm 0.89
9	17.76	6.2 \pm 0.84	11.4 \pm 0.55
10	19.98	5.6 \pm 0.55	10.4 \pm 0.89
11	22.20	5.2 \pm 0.84	9.0 \pm 0.71

$P < 0.05$; Each value represents the Mean \pm Standard Deviation (SD) of 10 replicates in three repeated experiments, **BAP**= Benzyl Amino Purine, **M-M**= Multiplication to Multiplication, **M-R**= Multiplication to Rooting.

Table 3. Efficiency of MS ½ medium with different concentrations of IBA in the induction of roots from *in vitro* derived shoots of *C. procera*.

S.No.	IBA (μM)	Percentage of root induction (Mean \pm SD)	Days to root formation	No. of roots / microshoots (Mean \pm SD)	Length of roots (cm) (Mean \pm SD)
1	0.0	40.0 \pm 1.33	26–28	1.5 \pm 0.53	2.8 \pm 0.64
2	2.46	81.1 \pm 1.20	20–22	3.0 \pm 0.94	4.7 \pm 0.41
3	4.92	92.6 \pm 0.52	16–18	5.8 \pm 0.42	12.9 \pm 0.91
4	9.84	80.8 \pm 1.03	20–22	4.6 \pm 0.52	8.8 \pm 0.97
5	14.76	80.4 \pm 0.84	22–24	3.3 \pm 0.48	8.7 \pm 0.89
6	19.68	75.1 \pm 0.74	22–24	2.6 \pm 0.52	7.6 \pm 1.07
7	24.60	70.0 \pm 0.94	22–24	2.3 \pm 0.48	7.0 \pm 0.95

$P < 0.01$; Each value represents the Mean \pm Standard Deviation (SD) of 10 replicates in three repeated experiments, IBA= Indole-3-butyric acid.

Fig.1 Axillary shoot bud regeneration on MS + BAP 13.32 μM

Fig.2 Shoot multiplication on MS + BAP 13.32 μM

Fig. 3 Rooting on MS $\frac{1}{2}$ + IBA 4.92 μM

Fig. 4 *In vitro* hardening

Fig. 5 *Ex vitro* hardening

Fig. 6 Potted Plants

DISCUSSION

Previous studies revealed that Callus induction of *Gymnema sylvestris* (Asclepiadaceae) using internodal explants and the influence of different plant hormones like 2,4-D, Kin, IAA, BAP on the growth of calli was observed by Roy et al. (2008) best results were observed on 2,4-D in combination with Kin (1-5 mg/l in 1:1 ratio). *In vitro* studies on the effect of plant growth regulators on callus and suspension culture for the yield of biomass of *Gymnema sylvestris* (Asclepiadaceae) states that callus induction was observed in MS medium containing basic salts and 30 g/l sucrose supplemented with 0.5 mg/l of 2,4-D from nodal segments and leaf explants (Gopi and Vatsala, 2006). Protocol for *in vitro* regeneration in *Cryptolepis buchanani* (Asclepiadaceae) was developed by Prasad et al. (2004) using shoot tip, cotyledonary node and nodal explants derived from seedlings grown *in vitro*. The best response was achieved with nodal explants in the form of maximum number of shoots (12.5 to 13.0 shoots/explant with a shoot length of 4.5 to 5.0 cm) on MS+BAP 2.0 mg/l, Kin 0.1 mg/l, NAA 0.05 mg/l and GA₃ 0.05 mg/l with 60 % response. The individual shoots were then rooted on MS medium supplemented with IBA 1 mg/l resulted in higher number of microshoots (80 %). The *in vitro* raised plantlets were acclimatized successfully to pots containing a mixture of autoclaved peatmoss and compost in 1:1 ratio. *in vitro* propagation of the aromatic and medicinal plant *Hemidesmus indicus* (Asclepiadaceae) from nodal explants has been developed by Patnaik and Debata (1996) which describes that the highest shoot multiplication rate with 95 % frequency was achieved in 5 weeks culture period on MS medium supplemented with 1.15 µM Kin and 0.054 µM NAA. The excised shoots were rooted on the same MS basal medium supplemented with 1.15 µM Kin and 7.35 µM IBA. After a hardening phase of 2 weeks, there was a 70 % transplantation success in the field. Tissue culture protocol of *Tylophora indica* (Asclepiadaceae) was established by many workers on MS medium (Chattopadhyay et al., 1992; Faisal and Anis, 2003, 2005; Nema et al., 2007)

However, to our knowledge, this is the first report for *in vitro* regeneration of *C. procera* through axillary shoot buds on MS semisolid medium + BAP 13.32 µM and also enables 81% survival of tissue culture raised plants from rooting to field conditions which can serve as raw material for pharmaceutical industries and sufficiently fulfills the demand isolation of target biochemicals of *C. procera* for human welfare.

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REFERENCE

- Anitha, S. and Pullaiah, T. 2002: *In vitro* propagation of *Decalepis hamiltonii*. Jounal of Tropical Medicinal Plants, 3: 227-232.
- Bais, H. P., J. George and G.A. Ravishankar. 2000. *In vitro* propagation of *Decalepis hamiltonii* Wight & Arn. an endangered shrub, through axillary bud culture. Curr. Sci. 79: 408-410.
- Chattopadhyay, S., Datta, S. K. and Ray, M. 1992: *In vitro* effect of NH₄NO₃ on growth and alkaloid content of *Tylophora indica* Merr. Phytomorphology, 42: 134-144.
- Chattopadhyay, S., Datta, S. K. and Ray, M. 1992: *In vitro* effect of NH₄NO₃ on growth and alkaloid content of *Tylophora indica* Merr. Phytomorphology, 42: 134-144.
- Faisal, M. and Anis, M. 2003: Rapid mass propagation of *Tylophora indica* Merrill via leaf callus culture. Plant Cell, Tissue and Organ Culture, 75: 125-129.
- Faisal, M. and Anis, M. 2005: An efficient *in vitro* method for mass propagation of *Tylophora indica*. Biologia Plantarum, 49: 257-260.
- Gopi, C. and Vatsala, T. M. 2006: *In vitro* studies on effects of plant growth regulators on callus and suspension culture biomass yield from *Gymnema sylvestre* R.Br. African Journal of Biotechnology, 5: 1215-1219.
- Joshi, R., Sharma, A. and Jat, B. L. 2009: Analysis of antioxidant activity in extracts of *Calotropis procera* (Ait.) R.Br. Journal of Applied Biosciences, 17: 899-903.
- Juncker, T., Schumacher, M., Dicato, M. and Diederich, M. 2009: UNBS1450 from *Calotropis procera* as a regulator of signaling pathways involved in proliferation and cell death. [Biochemical Pharmacology](#), 78: 1-10.
- Komalavalli, N. and Rao, M. V. 1997: *In vitro* micropropagation of *Gymnema elegans* Wt. & Arn.-A rare medicinal plant. Journal of Experimental Biology, 35: 1088-1092.

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- Kumar, V. L. and Arya, S. 2006: Medicinal uses and pharmacological properties of *Calotropis procera*. In: Govil, J. N. (Ed.) Recent progress in medicinal plants. Studium Press, Texas, 11: 373-388.
- Larhsini, M., Bousaid, M., Lazrek, H. B., Jana, M. and Amarouch, H. 1997: Evaluation of antifungal and molluscicidal properties of extracts of *Calotropis procera*. Fitoterapia, 68: 371-373.
- Martin, K. P. 2002. Rapid propagation of *Holostemma ada-kodien* Schult., a rare medicinal plant, through axillary bud multiplication and indirect organogenesis. Plant Cell Rep. 21: 112-117.
- Mueen Ahmed, K. K., Rana, A. C. and Dixit, V. K. 2005: *Calotropis* species (Asclepiadaceae)- A comprehensive review. Pharmacognosy Magazine, 1: 48-52.
- Mulabagal, V. and Tsay, H. S. 2004: Plant cell cultures an alternative and efficient source for the production of biologically important secondary metabolites. International Journal of Applied Sciences and Engineering, 2: 29-48.
- Murashige, T. and Skoog, F. 1962: A revised medium for rapid growth and bio assays with tobacco tissue culture. Physiologia Plantarum, 15: 473-497.
- Nema, R. K., Ramawat, K. G., Gupta, G. D., Tanwar, Y. S. and Mathur, M. 2007: Rapid Micropropagation of *Tylophora indica*. Pharmacognosy Magazine, 3: 52-55.
- Patnaik, J. and Debata, B.K. 1996: Micropropagation of *Hemidesmus indicus* (L.) R. Br. through axillary bud culture. Plant Cell Reports, 15: 427-430.
- Pramanik, T. K., De, S., Dasgupta, M. and Datta, S. K. 1986: Organ induced cardenolides biosynthesis in cultured tissues of *Asclepias curassavica*, *Calotropis gigantea* and *Thevetia peruviana*. International Congress of Plant Tissue, Cell Culture 6 meet, p. 115.
- Prasad, P. J. N., Chakradhar, T. and Pullaiah, T. 2004: Micropropagation of *Cryptolepis buchanani* Roem. & Schult. Taiwanica, 49: 57-65.
- Raghu Ramulu, D., Sri Rama Murthy, K. and Pullaiah, T. 2002: *In vitro* propagation of *Cynanchum callialatum*. Journal of Tropical Medicinal Plants, 3: 233-238.
- Ramos, M. V., Bandeira, G. P., Freitas, C. D. T., Nogueira, N. A. P., Alencar, N. M. N, Sousa, P. A. S. and Carvalho, A. F. U. 2006: Latex constituents from *Calotropis procera*

- (R. Br.) display toxicity upon egg hatching and larvae of *Aedes aegypti* (Linn.).
Memorias do Instituto Oswaldo Cruz, 101: 503-510.
- Roy, A., Ghosh, S., Chaudhuri, M. and Saha, P. K. 2008: Effect of different plant hormones on callus induction in *Gymnema sylvestris* R. Br. (Asclepiadaceae). African Journal of Biotechnology, 7: 2209-2211.
- Sharma, P. C. and M. B. Yelne. 1995. Observation on *in vitro* propagation of sarivas *Hemidesmus Indicus* R. Br. Bull. Medico Ethnobotanical Res. 16: 129-132.
- Sudha, C. G., P. N. Krishnan and P. Pushpangadan. 1998. *In vitro* propagation of *Holostemma annulare* (Roxb.) K. Schum, a rare medicinal plant. In vitro cell. Dev. Biol. Plant. 33: 57-63.
- Van Quaquebeke, E., Simon, G., Andre, A., Dewelle, J., Yazidi, M. E., Bruyneel, F., Tuti, J., Nacoulma, O., Guissou, P., Decaestecker, C., Braekman, J. C., Kiss, R. and Darro, F. 2005: Identification of a novel cardenolide (2-oxovoroscharin) from *Calotropis procera* and the hemisynthesis of novel derivatives displaying potent *in vitro* antitumor activities and high *in vivo* tolerance: structureactivity relationship analyses. Journal of Medicinal Chemistry, 48: 849-856.
- Yamada Y., Shoyama Y., Nishioka I., Kohda H., Namera A., Okamoto T., *Chem. Pharm. Bull.*, 39, 204—206 (1991).